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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	1
Executive summary.....	1
1. Introduction	1
2. Published resources.....	5
2.1 Original version.....	5
2.2 Croatian language version	8
2.3 Mirror sites	11

Executive summary

The GUTTA project final workshop “Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation” took place in Lecce, Italy, on May 4, 2022. This deliverable documents the press release and other dissemination actions related to this event, done both in Italy and Croatia.

1. Introduction

The GUTTA project final workshop “[Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation](#)” took place in Lecce on May 4, 2022 (see RP7 report on communication activities and Deliverable D.2.3.1 – Final report on the outcome of all GUTTA public events for further detail). The workshop involved several experts coming from different European countries in order to present the state of the art of maritime decarbonisation from multiple viewpoints: the regulatory institutions, the research and academia, the industry, and an environmental NGO. A special focus on the impact of COVID-19 on the maritime sector was made, and how it may have affected its pathway towards its decarbonisation. Indeed, the workshop provided insights on how the measures to address the COVID-19 pandemic impacted maritime transport, presenting several scientific studies and research. As a case study, the workshop presented the results of a study exploring the possible role of ferries in triggering the second wave of COVID-19 in Croatia, showing that this was not the case. The workshop was endorsed by IOC-UNESCO in the framework of the [UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development \(2021-2030\)](#) and by the

European Commission as an event of the initiative “European Maritime Day in my Country” ([#EMDin My Country](#)).

It was a high-level international event and represented the final act of the project to present its results at the public opinion. More than 300 persons attended the event both in-presence and online (see the agenda of the workshop at the end of this chapter – Figure 1). The day of the workshop, a press release, both in English and Italian language, has been prepared by the CMCC Communication Office. It has also been translated into Croatian language and published online on several websites.

Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonization

Wednesday, 4 May 2022, 9:00-17:00 CEST

Location: Via Marco Biagi 5, Lecce (and online)

Session A	Introduction
9:00	Welcome and moderation <i>Marina Lalovic (Journalist at RAI – Radiotelevisione Italiana – Rainews24)</i>
9:10	Institutional greetings/1 <i>Alessandro Delli Noci (Regione Puglia, Councillor)</i>
9:20	Institutional greetings/2 <i>Maja Markovčić Kostelac, video-message (EMSA, Director)</i>
9:30	An overview of the GUTTA project <i>Paola Agostini (CMCC, Senior Scientific Manager)</i>
Session B	Decarbonisation
9:40	keynote Reduction of CO ₂ emissions from shipping <i>Tristan Smith, online (UCL Energy Institute, Associate Professor and UMAS, Director)</i>
10:10	EU legislative proposals for maritime decarbonisation <i>Maria Alfayate, online (EU Commission, DG-Clima, Policy Officer)</i>
10:30	Coffee break
11:00	EU shipping proposals: fit for maritime decarbonisation? <i>Delphine Gozillon (T&E, Sustainable Shipping Policy Officer)</i>
11:20	Maritime decarbonisation: European framework and shipyards perspective in Italy <i>Chiara Notaro (CETENA, Research and WATERBORNE, Board)</i>
11:40	The GUTTA-VISIR service for least-CO ₂ ferry routes <i>Gianandrea Mannarini (CMCC, Senior Scientist)</i>

12:00	Panel discussion <i>All speakers of Session B, chaired by Marina Lalovic</i>
13:00	Lunch
Session C	COVID-19
14:30	Digitisation in Ports and Shipping at the time of COVID-19 <i>Michele Fiorini (IET-Italy, Chair)</i>
14:50	The pandemic's impact on global maritime mobility <i>Paolo Braca, online (NATO STO-CMRE, Senior Research Scientist)</i>
15:10	The Epidemic Renormalization Group and people mobility in the Adriatic region <i>Giacomo Cacciapaglia (CNRS, Senior Researcher)</i>
15:40	Statistical modelling of COVID-19 impact on maritime carbon emissions <i>Alessandro Fassò (University of Bergamo, Full Professor)</i>
16:00	Panel discussion <i>All speakers of Session C, chaired by Marina Lalovic</i>
16:45	Final remarks <i>Marina Lalovic</i>
	End of session C expected at 17:00

Figure 1: The agenda of GUTTA final workshop "Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation" held on May 4, 2022..

2. Published resources

The Press release includes an overview of the workshop, and an in-depth presentation of the project and its main outcomes: 1) the [GUTTA-VISIR](#) operational system for computing least-CO2 ferry routes in the Adriatic and Northern Ionian seas, based on meteo-oceanographic forecasting products of the Copernicus Marine service; 2) The [assessment of COVID-19 impacts on ferry transport](#) in the whole Europe.

The final video of the project, a video realized [in English](#), [in Italian](#), and [in English – subtitled in Croatian](#), and illustrating all the functionalities of GUTTA-VISIR, was also presented.

The original Press release was published on the CMCC website and on GUTTA webpage on the Interreg Italy Croatia website (Sect. 2.1). Later on, it was translated into Croatian (Sect.2.2) and was mirrored by several online magazines (Sect.2.3).

2.1 Original version

The screenshots in Figure 2-3 document the web environment where the press release appeared.

The English version is found at the URL:

<https://www.cmcc.it/article/towards-a-more-sustainable-maritime-transport-research-and-innovation-for-route-optimization-in-puglia-and-in-croatia>

cmcc.it/article/towards-a-more-sustainable-maritime-transport-research-and-innovation-for-route-optimization-in-puglia-and-in-croatia

Towards a more sustainable maritime transport: research and innovation for route optimization in Puglia and in Croatia

04/05/2022

Is it possible to improve and enhance maritime transport and, at the same time, contribute to reduce emissions in the field of mobility? The pathway towards a more sustainable ferry transportation can now benefit from a new and effective routing tool. This is thanks to the GUTTA project – saving fuel and emissions from marITime Transport in the Adriatic region, funded by the Interreg Italy-Croatia Programme, and coordinated by the CMCC Foundation. The major outcomes of the project were presented today during a workshop open to the public.

[Images at the following link](#)

LECCE, 4 May 2022 – The project GUTTA – saving fuel and emissions from marITime Transport in the Adriatic region, funded by the Interreg V-A Italy-Croatia Programme presented its results today during the public workshop “Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation”. The GUTTA project aims at reducing the carbon footprint of ferry routes between Italy and Croatia, by means of an automated route optimization tool, to enhance cross-border connectivity, and assess the role of COVID-19 on ferry transportation. During the workshop, the project illustrated GUTTA-VISIR, the decision support system devised for computing least-CO2 ferry routes in the Adriatic Sea.

The event involved several experts coming from different European countries in order to present the state of the art of maritime decarbonisation from multiple viewpoints: the regulatory institutions, the research and academia, the industry, and an environmental NGO. A special focus on the impact of COVID-19 on the maritime sector was made, and how it may have affected its pathway towards its decarbonisation. Indeed, the workshop provided insights on how the measures to address the COVID-19 pandemic impacted maritime transport, presenting several scientific studies and research. As a case study, the workshop presented the results of a study exploring the possible role of ferries in triggering the second wave of COVID-19 in Croatia, showing that this was not the case.

The project

GUTTA is a cross-border cooperation project, including in its consortium actors from academia, the industry, and the public sector

Figure 2: Screenshot of the English version of the CMCC webpage hosting the GUTTA final press release.

The Italian version is found at the URL:

<https://www.cmcc.it/it/articolo/verso-una-maggiore-sostenibilita-del-trasporto-marittimo-ricerca-e-innovazione-per-lottimizzazione-delle-rotte-in-puglia-e-in-croazia>

Figure 3: Screenshot of the Italian version of the CMCC webpage hosting the GUTTA final press release

Both English and Italian version were also disseminated through GUTTA and CMCC mailing lists. The CMCC newsletters are distributed to 25000 email addresses, and in particular: 15.000 contacts (English database); 10.000 contacts (Italian database), including the following categories: 18.000 Research & Academia; 3000 Media; 1500 NGO & Associations; 2500 Policy & Public Institution

The English version is available [at the following LINK](#)

The Italian version is available [at the following LINK](#)

The English version of the Press release was also published [on GUTTA webpage on the Interreg Italy Croatia website](#)

2.2 Croatian language version

The Press release has also been translated into Croatian by University of Zadar and published on University of Zadar and CSA mare nostrum websites at:

<https://uzz.unizd.hr/archive/view/lecce-4-svibnja-2022-rezultati-projekta-gutta-saving-fuel-and-emissions-from-maritime-transport-in-the-adriatic-region>

<http://www.csamarenostum.hr/hr/dogadanja/> (Figure 4-5).

CENTAR ZA PROJEKTE, ZNANOST I TRANSFER TEHNOLOGIJA

INFORMACIJE

- O nama
- Kontakti
- Obavijesti
- Prijave projekata
- Otvoreni natječaji
- Znanstveno-istraživački projekti
- Infrastrukturni projekti
- Institucionalni projekti
- Transfer tehnologija
- Korisni linkovi
- EURAXESS
- Festival znanosti 2022
- Otvorene molbe

Obavijesti

Trenutni članci [2](#) Arhiva [2](#) Pretraživanje [2](#) Preuzimanje (RSS) [2](#)

LECCE, 4. svibnja 2022. – Rezultati projekta GUTTA - savinG fUel and emissions from mariTime Transport in the Adriatic region

5. svibnja 2022.

Obavijesti

Prema održivom pomorskom prometu: Istraživanje i inovacije u svrhu optimizacije ruta u Puglia i Hrvatskoj

Je li moguće unaprijediti i poboljšati pomorski promet te istovremeno pridonijeti smanjenju emisija u području mobilnosti? Put prema održivom trajektnom prijevozu sada može imati koristi od nove i učinkovite web usluge za određivanje povoljne rute broda. To je moguće zahvaljujući projektu GUTTA - savinG fUel and emissions from mariTime Transport in the Adriatic region, kojeg financira Interreg program Italija-Hrvatska, a koordinira Zaklada CMCC. Glavni rezultati projekta predstavljani su tijekom radionice otvorene za javnost.

LECCE, 4. svibnja 2022. – Rezultati projekta GUTTA - savinG fUel and emissions from mariTime Transport in the Adriatic region, koji je financiran od strane Interreg V-A programa Italija-Hrvatska, predstavljani su na javnoj radionici „Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation“. Projekt GUTTA ima za cilj smanjenje ugljičnog otiska na trajektnim linijama između Italije i Hrvatske pomoću automatiziranog alata za optimizaciju ruta, poboljšati prekograničnu povezanost i procijeniti uloga COVID-19 u trajektnom prijevozu. Tijekom radionice, prikazana je web aplikacija za podršku u odlučivanju GUTTA-VISIR osmišljena tako da izračunava trajektnu rutu s najmanje CO₂ u Jadranskom moru.

Figure 4: Croatian translation of the Press release published on the University of Zadar website.

Non sicuro | csamarenostrum.hr/hr/događanja/

MARE NOSTRUM HRVATSKA UDRUGA BRODARA MARE NOSTRUM

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[BRODOMAT](#)
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Događanja

01.07.2022

Rezultati projekta GUTTA - saving fuel and emissions from marITime Transport in the Adriatic region

Prema održivom pomorskom prometu: Istraživanje i inovacije u svrhu optimizacije ruta u Puglia i Hrvatskoj

Je li moguće unaprijediti i poboljšati pomorski promet te istovremeno pridonijeti smanjenju emisija u području mobilnosti? Put prema održivom trajektnom prijevozu sada može imati koristi od nove i učinkovite web usluge za određivanje povoljne rute broda. To je moguće zahvaljujući projektu GUTTA - saving fuel and emissions from marITime Transport in the Adriatic region, kojeg financira Interreg program Italija-Hrvatska, a koordinira Zaklada CMCC. Glavni rezultati projekta predstavljani su tijekom radionice otvorene za javnost.

01.07.2022 [Detaljnije](#)

Hrvatska udruga brodara Mare Nostrum proslavila 30 godina rada: „To nije samo naš posao, nego životni poziv“

Dana 2. lipnja 2022. godine održana je 30. obljetnica Hrvatske udruge brodara Mare Nostrum

06.06.2022 [Detaljnije](#)

Završna konferencija GUTTA projekta u Italiji

Dana 4. svibnja 2022. godine u Lecceu, Italiji je održana završna konferencija povodom GUTTA projekta pod nazivom: "Putovanje kapljice u ocean dekarbonizacije".

09.05.2022 [Detaljnije](#)

Završni video GUTTA projekta

Užbudeni smo što možemo predstaviti završni video GUTTA projekta!

12.04.2022 [Detaljnije](#)

LECCE, 4. svibnja 2022. – Rezultati projekta *GUTTA - saving fuel and emissions from marITime Transport in the Adriatic region*, koji je financiran od strane Interreg V-A programa Italija-Hrvatska, predstavljani su na javnoj radionici *„Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation“*. Projekt GUTTA ima za cilj smanjenje ugljičnog otiska na trajektnim linijama između Italije i Hrvatske pomoću automatiziranog alata za optimizaciju ruta, poboljšati prekograničnu povezanost i procijeniti uloga COVID-19 u trajektnom

Figure 5: Croatian translation of the Press release published on CSA mare nostrum website.

2.3 Mirror sites

La Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno, one of the most important Italian newspapers, dedicated three articles to GUTTA final workshop and its outcomes (Read: [News1](#); [News2](#); [News3](#)), Figure 6).

Figure 6: An extract of the article published by Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno, based on the Italian version of the Press Release and interviews to main project partners, such as Gianandrea Mannarini, GUTTA sc. leader.

The online magazine leceprima.it, one of the most important online magazine in the Apulia region and in particular in the municipalities of Lecce and Brindisi, published a news about

GUTTA final workshop and its results ([Read](#)). They claim “1,2 millions readers and 6,1 millions monthly visits” ([Chi siamo](#); see Figure 7)

Figure 7: An extract of the article published by lecceprima.it, based on the Italian version of the Press Release.

GUTTA final workshop was able to involve young generations, and in particular some high school students of the municipality of Lecce attended the event in presence. Therefore, the magazine of the high school “Liceo Scientifico Statale Giulietta Banzi Bazoli” dedicated a news on the event ([Read](#); see Figure 8).

liceobanzi.edu.it/notizie/42-news/3422-journey-of-a-droplet-to-the-ocean-of-decarbonisation-a-cura-del-centro-euro-mediterraneo-sui-cambiamenti-climatici...

Liceo Scientifico Statale Giulietta Banzi Bazoli

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"Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation" a cura del Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC)

Pierandrea Bernardini e Andrea Capone della 4B, Melissa Foligno e Martina Monte della 4D, Jacopo Miglietta, della 4H ed Ettore Manca della 4L, accompagnati dalle docenti di Scienze Naturali, prof.sse Loredana Palma e Marina Tsagaki, il 4 maggio hanno partecipato all'evento organizzato presso la sede centrale CMCC di Lecce.

Gli studenti hanno avuto così l'opportunità di analizzare il cambiamento climatico attraverso un approccio globale e multidisciplinare. L'obiettivo del convegno era utilizzare il metodo scientifico per capire le prospettive climatiche ed anticipare in modo affidabile l'impatto ambientale che la decarbonizzazione potrebbe avere nel prossimo futuro.

La sfida ambientale, come ben sappiamo, non è facilmente risolvibile poiché coinvolge dinamiche complesse tra il pianeta e i suoi abitanti. Sebbene la conoscenza di queste dinamiche sia notevolmente avanzata è necessario affrontare con notevole rigore scientifico lo studio e l'analisi degli squilibri ambientali esistenti. Si comprende bene come in tale ambito il ruolo della ricerca sia fondamentale.

L'evento ha visto interventi da parte di ricercatori del CMCC e di altri importanti centri di ricerca; presiedevano il dott. G. Mannarini e la dott.ssa P. Agostini.

Numerose le presenze di professori universitari e di membri di rinomate aziende nell'ambito della ricerca e del trasporto marittimo, nonché significativa la relazione della dott.ssa Markovčić Kostelac, direttrice EMSA (agenzia europea che ha il compito di ridurre il rischio di incidenti marittimi e di inquinamento marino causato dalle navi).

Il tema affrontato ha riscosso un grande successo anche in termini di risonanza mediatica, tanto da coinvolgere la partecipazione di Rainews24 nella figura della moderatrice dell'evento e giornalista M. Lalovic. Il convegno è stato reso pubblico in diretta su piattaforma youtube.

L'esperienza è stata particolarmente gradita ai nostri alunni che hanno partecipato attivamente al dibattito offrendo, inoltre, interessanti spunti ai relatori attraverso domande pertinenti all'interno del forum.

Figure 8: An extract of the article published by Liceo Banzi Bazoli magazine.

The Croatian [Novi List](#) (print run 24000 copies) also dedicated a news to GUTTA final workshop (Figure 9).

Figure 9: An extract of the article published by Novi List, based on the Croatian version of the Press Release.

Here the list of media appearances related to GUTTA final workshop:

4/05/2022 - [Puglia pioniera delle rotte rispettose dell'ambiente - La Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno](#)

4/05/2022 - [Un milione e 5 partner internazionali - La Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno](#)

4/05/2022 - [Verso la sostenibilità del trasporto marittimo: una ricerca tra Lecce e la Croazia - lecceprima.it](#)
[Read online](#)

4/05/2022 - [Verso una maggiore sostenibilità del trasporto marittimo - meteoweb.eu](#)
[Read online](#)

4/05/2022 - [Verso un trasporto marittimo più sostenibile: ricerca per l'ottimizzazione delle rotte in Puglia e Croazia - esgdata.it](#)
[Read online](#)

5/05/2022 - [Rotte green nell ' Adriatico con il «cervellone» leccese - La Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno](#)

6/05/2022 - [Maggiore sostenibilità del trasporto marittimo tra Italia e Croazia - freshplaza.it](#)

[10/05/2022 - "Journey of a droplet to the ocean of decarbonisation" a cura del Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici \(CMCC\) – Liceobanzi.edu.it](#)

[12/06/2022 - Detalji važnog hrvatsko-talijanskog projekta "pametne plovidbe": Kako smanjiti potrošnju goriva i emisije CO2](#)